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Clinical paper

Occurrence of shockable rhythm in out-of-hospital cardiac arrest over time: A report from the COSTA group

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Abstract

Background: Prior research suggests that the proportion of a shockable initial rhythm in out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) declined during the last decades. This study aims to investigate if this decline is still ongoing and explore the relationship between location of OHCA and proportion of a shockable initial rhythm as initial rhythm.

Methods: We calculated the proportion of patients with a shockable initial rhythm between 2006–2015 using pooled data from the COSTA-group (Copenhagen, Oslo, Stockholm, Amsterdam). Analyses were stratified according to location of OHCA (residential vs. public).

Results: A total of 19,054 OHCA cases were included. Overall, the total proportion of cases with a shockable initial rhythm decreased from 42% to 37% ($P < 0.01$) from 2006 to 2015. When stratified according to location, the proportion of cases with a shockable initial rhythm decreased for OHCA at a residential location (34% to 27%; $P = 0.03$), while the proportion of a shockable initial rhythm was stable among OHCA in public locations (59%–57%; $P = 0.2$). During the last years of the study period (2011–2015), the overall proportion of a shockable initial rhythm remained stable (38%–37%; $P = 0.45$); this was observed for both residential and public OHCA.

Conclusion: We found a decline in the proportion of patients with a shockable initial rhythm in OHCA at a residential location; this decline levelled off during the second half of the study period (2011–2015). In public locations, we observed no decline in shockable initial rhythm over time.

Keywords: Cardiac arrest, Out-of-hospital, Decline, Shockable rhythm, COSTA

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Introduction

A shockable initial rhythm (SIR) is one of the most important predictors of survival after an out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA). Patients with a SIR are more likely to survive if they are quickly defibrillated.¹ However, multiple reports suggest that the proportion of SIR in OHCA has declined worldwide and rates of SIR as low as 24% have been reported.^{2–6}

A decline in proportion of SIR may be caused by lower occurrence of a SIR at initial collapse, which has been suggested by prior research.⁴ Another explanation of lower observed rates of SIR is longer delays to first electrocardiographic (ECG) recording. As time from collapse passes, SIR will eventually degenerate into asystole. Thus, patients presenting in asystole may have actually had a SIR at the time of the collapse. Such a delay (e.g. caused by longer response intervals and/or lower rates of witnessed collapse) is generally longer in OHCA occurring at a residential location, as opposed to those occurring in a public location.^{7,8} In addition, OHCA patients at a residential location are older and have more comorbidities that may result in lower rate of a SIR.⁹ Because these OHCA patients may also face the abovementioned decline in proportion of a SIR, the question has arisen whether public access defibrillation initiatives to involve automated external defibrillators (AED) in the resuscitation effort are worthwhile for OHCA patients at a residential location.¹⁰

Therefore, it is important to study whether the decline in proportion of SIR is continuing. This study aims to determine whether the proportion of SIR is still declining over a 10-year time period up to 2016 across multiple emergency medical services (EMS) in four different European countries. Secondly, this study aims to determine whether this decline in proportion of SIR is different between OHCA occurring at a residential location and those at public locations.

Methods

COSTA group

The COSTA group is a collaboration network of resuscitation researchers in Copenhagen (Denmark), Oslo (Norway), Stockholm (Sweden), and Amsterdam (the Netherlands), which aims at joining research efforts in OHCA and early defibrillation. Data from OHCA events across all COSTA sites were merged and analyzed in a central research database within the COSTA collaboration. This study was performed in line with the Helsinki declaration.¹¹ Ethical approval was granted by the ethical boards for each study site.

Setting, study regions and emergency medical service systems

Denmark: central Copenhagen

Central Copenhagen covers 97 km² and holds approximately 680,000 inhabitants. Incidence of OHCA was 81 cases per 100,000 in 2014. The EMS of Copenhagen is a two-tiered system comprising ambulances equipped with defibrillators providing basic life support (BLS) and physician-staffed mobile emergency care units providing advanced life support (ALS). OHCA patients with an EMS resuscitation attempt are included in the registry. Also, OHCA patients with AED defibrillation by bystanders only (either with or without return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC) at arrival of the ambulance) are

Table 1 – Baseline and resuscitation characteristics of OHCA patients with presumed cardiac cause.

Baseline characteristics	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	P for trend	Missing n (%)
Patients, n	1611	1631	1916	1884	1920	1852	1811	2042	2155	2332		
Copenhagen, n	NR	NR	352	414	362	315	256	271	286	252		
Oslo, n	158	130	56 ^a	NR	NR	NR	NR	144 ^b	287	263		
Stockholm, n	602	624	635	601	672	640	685	725	706	746		
North Holland, n	851	877	873	869	886	897	870	902	876	971		
Age ^c	69 (58, 79)	69 (58, 79)	68 (58, 79)	69 (59, 80)	70 (59, 80)	69 (58, 80)	69 (60, 80)	69 (60, 80)	70 (58, 80)	70 (60, 79)	<0.01	201 (1%)
Male sex ^d	1175 (73%)	1131 (69%)	1396 (70%)	1305 (69%)	1312 (69%)	1274 (69%)	1230 (68%)	1432 (70%)	1502 (70%)	1562 (70%)	0.44	42 (<1%)
Public location ^d	508 (32%)	498 (31%)	595 (31%)	560 (30%)	555 (29%)	550 (30%)	553 (31%)	652 (32%)	664 (31%)	699 (32%)	0.54	39 (<1%)
Bystander CPR ^d	897 (56%)	999 (62%)	1060 (57%)	1056 (57%)	1112 (59%)	1177 (64%)	1194 (67%)	1484 (73%)	1520 (71%)	1645 (74%)	<0.01	235 (1%)
Witnessed collapse ^d	1181 (74%)	1175 (73%)	1320 (70%)	1242 (67%)	1274 (68%)	1189 (66%)	1176 (66%)	1333 (67%)	1360 (64%)	1426 (65%)	<0.01	284 (1.5%)
Time call to scene arrival ^{c,e}	9 (7, 12)	10 (7, 13)	8 (6, 12)	8 (6, 12)	9 (6, 12)	8 (6, 11)	8 (6, 12)	9 (6, 12)	9 (6, 12)	8 (6, 11)	<0.01	2188 (11%)
Initial shockable rhythm ^d	665 (42%)	648 (41%)	681 (37%)	663 (36%)	708 (37%)	705 (38%)	640 (36%)	718 (36%)	754 (36%)	807 (37%)	<0.01	295 (2%)
AED defibrillation ^d	140 (9%)	159 (10%)	177 (9%)	206 (11%)	278 (15%)	336 (18%)	353 (20%)	358 (18%)	383 (18%)	456 (21%)	<0.01	82 (0.4%)

Abbreviations: AED, automated external defibrillator; CPR, cardio-pulmonary resuscitation; NR not reported.

^a Data represents 4 months.

^b Data represents 6 months.

^c Median (25th–75th percentile), trend in time tested using Jonckheere-Terpstra test.

^d Variables are denoted as cases (percentage), trend in time tested using Chi-square statistic.

^e Oslo, North Holland and Stockholm regions: time EMS call to scene arrival. Copenhagen region: time of dispatch of the first ambulance to scene arrival.

included in this registry. If already deceased, OHCA patients are not included in the registry. Only physicians can decide to terminate a resuscitation effort.

Norway: Oslo

Before 2009, Oslo EMS covered a population of approximately 550,000 inhabitants in 454 km², and was served with one-tiered ambulance service manned with paramedics and emergency medical technicians. Incidence of OHCA was 57 cases per 100,000 in 2014. After 2013, Oslo and Akershus EMS were merged to serve a population of approximately 1.2 million inhabitants in a mixed urban and rural area of 5371 km². Before 2013, OHCA patients were included if treatment by ambulance (either CPR for at least 30 s or defibrillation) was started. After 2013 the inclusion criteria changed to: treatment by either bystanders, first responders, or ambulance. Patients already deceased were not included in the registry. Paramedics may decide to terminate the resuscitation effort without consulting a physician, and declare death. OHCA patients with AED defibrillation only and ROSC at arrival of the ambulance were not included in the registry in the study period.

Sweden: Stockholm region

Stockholm region covers 6519 km² and has 2.1 million inhabitants. Incidence of OHCA was 38 cases per 100,000 per year in 2014. There is a two-tiered EMS system in Sweden for responses to all medical emergencies. Both tiers consist of EMS units with registered nurses in prehospital care providing ALS and with AED or manual defibrillation. All OHCA patients treated with CPR and/or defibrillation initiated by bystanders, first responders or EMS as well as OHCA patients with AED defibrillation only and ROSC at arrival of the ambulance are included in this registry. If already deceased, OHCA patients are not included in the registry. Paramedics may decide to terminate the resuscitation effort without consulting a physician, and declare death.

The Netherlands: province of North Holland

The province of North Holland covers 2404 km² and has 2.4 million inhabitants. Incidence of OHCA was 46 cases per 100,000 in 2014. In

response to an OHCA, two ambulances of a single tier are dispatched. Ambulance personnel are equipped with manual defibrillators and perform ALS. OHCA patients with AED defibrillation by bystanders or first responders only and ROSC at arrival of the ambulance are also included in this registry. If already deceased, OHCA patients are not included in the registry. Paramedics may decide to terminate the resuscitation effort without consulting a physician. If so, a physician comes to the scene to declare death. Also, OHCA patients are included in the registry only if they have been resuscitated by the EMS for >2 min.

Study question, study population and data collection

The primary purpose of this paper was to determine whether the proportion of SIR changed during the study period, and whether this differed between OHCA occurring at a residential or public location. We included patients in whom EMS personnel attempted resuscitation for OHCA between January 1, 2006 and December 31, 2015. We excluded patients with obvious non-cardiac cause of the arrest and EMS-witnessed OHCA. All registries used the Utstein template for data reporting.¹² For the Oslo region, only data from 2006 to 2008 and 2012 to 2015 were included, while for the Copenhagen region, only data from 2008 to 2015 were included, for reasons of availability. All data were anonymized and pooled into a central COSTA database.

Definitions

The initial rhythm recorded by EMS manual defibrillator or AED (whichever was first) was categorized as shockable (ventricular tachycardia, ventricular fibrillation or shock by an AED) or non-shockable (asystole, pulseless electrical activity). Outcome was defined as proportion of SIR rather than incidence of SIR, in order to attenuate effects of registry differences. Location of collapse was retrieved from EMS-call or dispatch form. All non-residential locations were considered public. Long term care facilities were classified as residential location. Time to EMS-arrival was defined as the difference between the time of the EMS-call to the dispatch centre and the time of

Fig. 1 – (A) Prehospital resuscitation characteristics per year in total. (B) Prehospital resuscitation characteristics per year at residential location. (C) Prehospital resuscitation characteristics per year in public. Abbreviations: AED, Automated external defibrillator; CPR, cardiopulmonary resuscitation.

Table 2 – Baseline and resuscitation characteristics of OHCA patients with presumed cardiac cause and residential location.

Baseline characteristics	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	P for trend	Missing n (%)
Patients, n	1100	1126	1319	1323	1362	1301	1257	1389	1487	1517		
Copenhagen, n	NR	NR	272	320	286	218	182	173	192	157		
Oslo, n	96	34 ^a	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	94 ^b	212	173		
Stockholm, n	409	420	429	396	445	438	455	503	484	500		
North Holland, n	595	616	584	607	631	645	620	619	599	687		
Age ^c	71 (59, 80)	70 (59, 80)	71 (60, 80)	71 (61, 81)	72 (62, 81)	71 (60, 81)	72 (62, 81)	71 (62, 81)	71 (61, 81)	72 (62, 81)	<0.01	61 (<1%)
Male sex ^d	747 (68%)	729 (65%)	843 (64%)	844 (64%)	866 (64%)	819 (63%)	785 (63%)	905 (65%)	966 (65%)	985 (65%)	0.56	17 (<1%)
Bystander CPR ^{b,d}	551 (50%)	646 (58%)	621 (49%)	648 (50%)	695 (52%)	731 (57%)	758 (61%)	951 (69%)	987 (67%)	1041 (69%)	<0.01	170 (1%)
Witnessed collapse ^d	769 (70%)	770 (69%)	857 (67%)	817 (63%)	855 (64%)	771 (61%)	760 (61%)	856 (63%)	870 (59%)	888 (59%)	<0.01	188 (1%)
Time call to scene arrival ^{c,e}	9 (7,12)	10 (8,13)	9 (6,12)	8 (6,12)	9 (6,12)	8 (6,11)	8 (6,11)	9 (7,12)	9 (6,12)	8 (6,11)	<0.01	1548 (12%)
Initial shockable rhythm ^d	370 (34%)	372 (33%)	357 (27%)	358 (28%)	382 (28%)	383 (30%)	333 (27%)	367 (27%)	407 (28%)	405 (27%)	<0.01	211 (2%)
AED defibrillation ^d	74 (7%)	80 (7%)	74 (6%)	86 (7%)	132 (10%)	153 (12%)	161 (13%)	161 (12%)	177 (12%)	214 (14%)	<0.01	61 (0.5%)

Abbreviations: AED, automated external defibrillator; CPR, cardio-pulmonary resuscitation; NR not reported.

^a Data represents 4 months.

^b Data represents 6 months.

^c Median (25th–75th percentile), trend in time tested using Jonckheere-Terpstra test.

^d Variables are denoted as cases (percentage), trend in time tested using Chi-square statistic.

^e Oslo, North Holland and Stockholm regions: time EMS call to scene arrival. Copenhagen region: time of dispatch of the first ambulance to scene arrival.

vehicle stop of the first ambulance, except for the Copenhagen region: here, time to EMS-arrival was defined as the differences between time of dispatch of the first ambulance and time of vehicle stop. Defibrillator connection time was defined as the time interval between EMS-call and connection of the defibrillator device to the patient (EMS manual defibrillator or AED, whichever came first; North Holland region only). Other resuscitation characteristics included were witnessed collapse, bystander CPR and defibrillation by AED.

Data analysis

Proportions of SIR, using the pooled COSTA database, were calculated for each study year (2006–2015), as well as for each study region separately. Categorical variables were presented as percentages and continuous variables as mean and standard deviation (SD) or as median and interquartile range (IQR) depending on the data distributions. To compare categorical data, the trend in time was tested using chi-square statistics. To compare continuous data, the trend in time was tested using the Jonckheere-Terpstra test. To determine whether trends were consistent during the study period, we separately analyzed the study years 2006–2010 (Period 1) and 2011–2015 (Period 2). In addition, analyses were stratified according to OHCA location.

Since the included OHCA cases originated from four different study regions, we performed a multilevel analysis to account for region effects. Furthermore, time trends in proportion of SIR were tested using regression analysis while adjusting for study region and/or resuscitation characteristics where applicable.

Finally, proportions of SIR were analyzed in relation to defibrillator connection time. All statistical tests were two-tailed, and a P-value of <0.05 was considered to be statistically significant. Statistics were performed in SPSS 24 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY).

Results

A total of 19,054 EMS-treated OHCA patients were included for analysis (Table 1), of which 13,181 (69%) occurred at a residential location (eTable 1) and 5834 (31%) in a public location (eTable 1). Baseline characteristics per study region are provided in eTables 2–5.

Demographic and resuscitation characteristics

Median age increased from 69 to 70 years (P for trend <0.01). Patients were more often male, proportions varying between 68% to 73% (P for trend=0.44) (Table 1). The proportion of witnessed collapse decreased from 74% to 65% (P for trend <0.01). The proportion of bystander CPR increased from 56% to 74% (P for trend <0.01), as well as the proportion of AED defibrillation which increased from 9% to 21% (P for trend <0.01) (Fig. 1A, Table 1). The proportion of OHCA occurring at public locations (Fig. 1A) did not change over time (Table 1). Stratification according to location showed that similar trends were observed for both OHCA occurring at residential (Fig. 1B, Table 2) and in public locations (Fig. 1C, Table 3). Both in public and residential locations, bystander CPR increased (public 69%–86%, residential: 50%–69%, both P for trend <0.01), as did AED defibrillation (public 13%–35%, residential: 7%–14%, both P for trend <0.01).

Table 3 – Baseline and resuscitation characteristics of OHCA patients with presumed cardiac cause and public location.

Baseline characteristics	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	P for trend	Missing n (%)
Patients, n	508	498	595	560	555	550	553	652	664	699		
Copenhagen, n	NR	NR	80	94	76	97	74	98	94	95		
Oslo, n	61	39	22 ^a	NR	NR	NR	NR ^b	50	72	88		
Stockholm, n	191	198	204	204	227	201	230	221	221	232		
North Holland, n	256	261	289	262	252	252	249	283	277	284		
Age ^c	65 (56, 75)	65 (56, 76)	64 (54, 75)	64 (55, 76)	65 (54, 74)	64 (55, 75)	66 (55, 75)	66 (55, 75)	65 (55, 76)	66 (55, 75)	0.55	137 (2%)
Male sex ^d	425 (84%)	398 (80%)	491 (83%)	461 (82%)	444 (80%)	454 (83%)	445 (81%)	527 (82%)	534 (81%)	568 (82%)	0.57	24 (<1%)
Bystander CPR ^{b,d}	346 (69%)	348 (70%)	437 (75%)	407 (73%)	414 (76%)	446 (82%)	436 (81%)	533 (82%)	530 (81%)	593 (86%)	<0.01	64 (1%)
Witnessed collapse ^d	411 (81%)	401 (81%)	461 (79%)	424 (76%)	416 (77%)	418 (78%)	416 (78%)	476 (75%)	487 (75%)	531 (77%)	0.01	93 (2%)
Time call to scene arrival ^{c,e}	9 (6,12)	9 (7,13)	8 (5,11)	8 (5,11)	8 (6,12)	8 (5,11)	9 (6,12)	9 (6,12)	9 (6,11)	8 (6,11)	0.04	637 (11%)
Initial shockable rhythm ^d	294 (59%)	274 (57%)	324 (56%)	305 (55%)	325 (60%)	321 (59%)	307 (56%)	350 (55%)	346 (53%)	399 (58%)	0.24	101 (2%)
AED defibrillation ^d	65 (13%)	79 (16%)	103 (18%)	120 (22%)	146 (26%)	182 (33%)	192 (35%)	197 (30%)	206 (31%)	242 (35%)	<0.01	20 (0.5%)

Abbreviations: AED, automated external defibrillator; CPR, cardio-pulmonary resuscitation; NR not reported.

^a Data represents 4 months.^b Data represents 6 months.^c Median (25th–75th percentile), trend in time tested using Jonckheere-Terpstra test.^d Variables are denoted as cases (percentage), trend in time tested using Chi-square statistic.^e Copenhagen data includes: time of dispatch of the first ambulance to vehicle stop.

Proportion of shockable initial rhythm

During the total study period the proportion of SIR decreased from 42% to 37% ($P < 0.01$) (Fig. 2A). When stratified according to OHCA location, the proportion of SIR decreased statistically significant for OHCA at a residential location (34%–27%; $P < 0.01$) (Fig. 2B), but not for OHCA in a public location (59%–57%; $P = 0.24$) (Fig. 2C).

Multilevel analysis indicated that study region did not affect the slope of the association between study year and proportion of SIR ($P < 0.05$). Accordingly, adding 'region' to a logistic regression with study year as determinant of SIR did not meaningfully affect the odds ratio (OR) of study year (OR_{unadjusted} study year = 1.019, $p < 0.001$; OR adjusted study year = 1.016, $p = 0.003$).

During Period 1, the total proportion of SIR declined (42%–37%; $P < 0.01$) (Fig. 2A). The proportion of SIR for OHCA at a residential location also declined (34%–28%; $P = 0.03$) (Fig. 2B), but remained stable for OHCA in a public location (59%–60%; $P = 0.53$) (Fig. 2C). However, during Period 2, there was no decrease in proportion of SIR, neither overall (38%–37%; $P = 0.45$) (Fig. 1A), nor when stratified according to location (residential: 30%–27%; $P = 0.40$; public location: 59%–58%; $P = 0.50$) [Fig. 2B, C].

To further explore a possible explanation of the stabilized proportion of SIR in the residential location, we separately analyzed resuscitation characteristics in Period 1 and Period 2. During Period 1 we observed a decrease in witnessed status ($P < 0.01$) but proportion of bystander CPR ($P = 0.33$) remained stable. During Period 2, we observed a stable proportion of witnessed status ($P = 0.17$) but the proportion of bystander CPR increased ($P < 0.01$) (eTable 6). However, adding bystander CPR to a logistic regression with year as determinant of SIR did not meaningfully affect the OR of study year (OR_{unadjusted} study year = 1.001, $P = 0.944$; OR_{adjusted} study year = 1.017, $P = 0.386$).

Proportion of shockable initial rhythm in relation to defibrillator connection time

Fig. 3 shows the proportion of SIR in relation to defibrillator connection time. If time from EMS-call to defibrillator connection was 8–10 min, the proportion of SIR was still 48% (95% CI 46–51). For this delay, the proportion of SIR for OHCA at a residential location was 41% (95% CI 38–43) and for OHCA in a public location 71% (95% CI 67–75). Results divided in Period 1 and Period 2 are shown in eFig. 1.

Discussion

Main findings

Over the total study period (2006–2015), the proportion of SIR declined in four regions from four European countries and this decline was primarily observed in OHCA at residential locations. However, when limiting the analysis to more recent study years (2011–2015), the proportion of SIR remained stable. When time from EMS-call to defibrillator connection time was short (8–10 min), the proportion of SIR was still high with 41% for OHCA at a residential location, and 71% for OHCA in a public location.

Levelling off of decline in SIR and prior literature

Although a decline in proportion of SIR was present in Period 1, we found that the decline in SIR has levelled off during Period 2. The decline

Fig. 2 – (A) Proportions shockable initial rhythm per year in total; and per region. (B) Proportions shockable initial rhythm per year at residential location; and per region. (C) Proportions shockable initial rhythm per year in public; and per region.

Abbreviations: SIR, shockable initial rhythm.

in SIR in Period 1 may result from an absolute decrease of patients at risk for SIR or from an absolute increase in non-SIR OHCA. First, an absolute decrease of patients at risk for a SIR may be a result of primary prevention measures and/or medical changes that resulted in improved treatment of ischemic heart disease (e.g., more use of β -adrenoceptor blockers) and/or more widespread use of implantable cardioverter defibrillators.^{4,13} Second, an absolute increase in non-SIR OHCA may result from population changes such as higher aged OHCA patients. Also, it has been suggested that co-morbidities such as obstructive pulmonary disease has been associated with non-SIR OHCA, whereby recent studies suggested an increasing disease burden in OHCA patients (in particular with advancing age).^{14,15}

The levelling off in the decline of the proportion of SIR observed in Period 2 may, at least partly, be influenced by an increasing rate of bystander CPR and the stabilized rate of witnessed status (while this rate decreased in Period 1). Being witnessed during collapse and an increased chance on receiving bystander CPR reduces the no-flow

time, which may lead to slower degeneration of a SIR.¹⁶ Nonetheless, these variables did not statistically explain the absence of decline in SIR during Period 2.

AED initiatives and presence of SIR

Controlled clinical trials have shown that the use of AEDs in public settings by trained citizen-responders improves survival after OHCA.¹⁷ OHCA patients at a residential location differ unfavorably from OHCA patients in a public location.^{7,18} In combination with a (presumed ongoing) decline in proportion of a SIR,⁴ this gave rise to the question whether AED initiatives are worthwhile for OHCA patients at residential locations.

Results from the present study showed that the observed decline in SIR has levelled off, in particular in OHCA occurring at a residential location. In addition, the present study adds important information, as we can demonstrate that the proportion of SIR in OHCA patients at a

Fig. 3 – Proportion shockable initial rhythm and time to defibrillator connection in minutes (2006–2015).

residential location with a short delay (8–10 min) between EMS-call and defibrillator connection is still high. This cut-off point of 8–10 min is important because many international EMS systems adopted a 8-minute response time for EMS units responding to life-threatening events (i.e., in order to maximize survival chances after OHCA).¹⁹

Furthermore, rates of AED defibrillation doubled during the study period. As previously shown, use of AEDs at a residential location decreases time from EMS-call to defibrillator connection and is associated with increased survival rates in patients with a SIR.²⁰ We therefore recommend continuous efforts to improve resuscitation care at residential locations, with strong emphasis on introducing or extending AED initiatives to facilitate early defibrillation (such as public access defibrillation programs).²¹ This recommendation is important, in particular, because approximately 70% of OHCA occur at a residential location while survival rates after OHCA occurring at home are significantly lower than after OHCA occurring in public places.⁸ Thus, for residential locations, even a modest increase in survival would have a substantial impact in absolute numbers of lives saved.

Differences in proportion of SIR across study sites

Differences in proportions of SIR have been observed across the study sites. This may be a result of regional differences in inclusion in the registry, since the definition of an EMS-treated OHCA differs across the sites. For instance, in the Netherlands, an OHCA is included in the registry if the OHCA is treated by the EMS for >2 min. The definition in Oslo includes a duration of >30 s EMS treatment and in Denmark no minimal duration is used. Therefore, the included proportion of OHCA with a worse prognosis may have been higher in the Scandinavian regions when compared to the Dutch region, resulting in a lower proportion of SIR. Also, OHCA patients with AED defibrillation only and ROSC at arrival of the ambulance were not included in the Oslo registry, whereas these cases (with high chances of presenting with a SIR) were included in the other registries. However, the use of AEDs was very low in the Oslo registry.

Limitations

Some important limitations need to be considered; first, as with all observational studies, we were only able to study associations. A causal relation between any of the variables studied cannot be determined in this cohort. Second, missing data occurred as not every site collected data of each study year (i.e., missing data for the years 2006–2007 [Copenhagen] and 2009–2012 [Oslo]). Finally, although all study regions used the Utstein template to collect data, differences may exist because of: (1) variation in the interpretation of the Utstein definitions; (2) regional differences in the EMS system and (3) differences in inclusion to the registries, as mentioned above. To attenuate the effect of these differences between participating study regions, we chose to use proportions instead of incidences. Also, we stratified results by study region and performed a multilevel analysis.

Strengths

A major strength of the present study is the comprehensiveness of the collected data sets, including data from EMS-dispatch centre, paramedics and hospital thereby providing a complete picture of the circumstances of the OHCA.

Conclusion

A small decline in proportion of SIR was observed in the study period 2006–2015, in particular in OHCA occurring at a residential location. In the second half of this study period (2011–2015), this decline has levelled off.

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Competing interests

None declared.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resuscitation.2020.03.014>.

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